

e-INFRA CZ Pilot Node

General-purpose HTC/HPC national research infrastructure

FACTSHEET FOR: Generic e-infrastructure and HTC/HPC users in research/academia

Pilot Node Profile

The e-INFRA CZ node is a distributed national computing infrastructure, comprising tens of thousands of CPUs overall, available in HPC, grid and cloud installations. It offers additional services too, such as datasets or tools for specific disciplines, and caters to thousands of users recruiting mainly from Czech academia.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
{production}
- **PID Service (National repository platform)**
{production}

Pilot Exchange Services

- **SaaS on Compute**
(cloud, storage, access instruments, workflow management)
- **IaaS Cloud**
(data management, storage)
- **Storage**
(National repository platform)

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

User story at-a-glance

A scientist, a forestry expert, gets invited by an international colleague to verify and replicate their research. The foreign author has released a dataset with an accompanying Jupyter notebook. They are a Czech national and they were using the services of e-INFRA CZ, their Czech academic infrastructure. They used the National Repository Platform to publish their research, and assign a PID (OID) to it. Also, the accompanying algorithm (notebook) is easiest to run in the neighbouring i-EINFRA CZ

Notebooks installation since it's guaranteed to have all the prerequisites in place.

The user in our user story can rely on the EOSC Node status of e-INFRA CZ, and log into the same environment their Czech colleague was using. They proceed to look up the dataset based on the DOI provided, retrieve the dataset, and run the attached notebook to review or tweak the original author's conclusions.

e-INFRA CZ Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integration with other nodes' AAI through Check-in – given that e-INFRA CZ is a distributed collection of services, they often require separate integration steps. In the current context the main integrations applicable are those of the infrastructure cloud service, notebooks service, and the National Repository Platform.

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- AAI

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- AAI

Value of the Node piloting activities

Easy interoperability and portability of skills and competences between nodes:

The pilot demonstrates how technical and operational expertise can be transferred across infrastructures. It supports common interfaces, containerized deployments, and reproducible workflows, enabling users and administrators to apply their knowledge consistently in different EOSC environments.

Cross-node access – seamless use and horizontal integration of unique services offered by distinct nodes:

The pilot promotes a federated approach where computing, data, and analytical services from separate

providers can be combined into unified workflows. This facilitates multidisciplinary research and simplifies access to specialized resources through shared authentication and service discovery.

Standardization and best practices across nodes:

By aligning with EOSC interoperability frameworks, the pilot contributes to defining reference models for service registration, monitoring, and accounting. The resulting guidelines will help future nodes integrate faster and more reliably, improving sustainability and reproducibility across the EOSC ecosystem.

Next steps

Additional services will need integrating as for the time being only IaaS Cloud and Notebooks are fully integrated with the AAI federation.

Additional components developed in Beyond, such as the service adapters, will be deployed in operation. This relates mainly to adapters for notebooks, which will be deployed in

the environment and configured to enable horizontal services in the ecosystem.

User documentation and examples will be expanded to cover in greater detail the inter-node scenarios now available.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

e-INFRA CZ Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/e-infra-cz>

e-INFRA CZ:

<https://www.e-infra.cz/en>

e-INFRA CZ Notebooks:

<https://jupyter.e-infra.cz/>